

Estimation of hydrogen peroxide content in Ophthalmic formulation using ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometry

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Abstract : The peroxide content in formulation products is crucial and needs to be monitored under various conditions since it may cause detrimental effect, especially when used in formulations containing drugs that are susceptible to oxidation. Moreover, determination of peroxide in such products is a prerequisite, listed both in the British as well as European Pharmacopoeia. The purpose of this study is to quantify the peroxide content in Ophthalmic formulation contain of 0.1% of Olopatadine drug used to treat itching and redness in the eyes due to allergies. The other ingredients along with drug in this formulation are polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), benzalkonium chloride, disodium orthophosphate, sodium chloride, ethylenediaminetetraacetate. Based on details of ingredients presents in Ophthalmic formulation, it is expected to contain of residual peroxides from either PVP or other in final formulation which may influence the chemical stability of formulated drug product. It is highly recommend having analytical method for quantification of peroxide for drug products. At present, European Pharmacopoeia has the quantification method for peroxide for plain excipient only not for drug products. A simple and precise method was developed for the determination of hydrogen peroxide levels in the Ophthalmic solutions using Ultraviolet-Visible spectrophotometer. The quantification of hydrogen peroxide was performed at 405 nm and linearity was established from 1.5 ppm to 400 ppm with accuracy of 95% to 105%. Three different formulations were studied using developed method and peroxide was found to be contains less than 10 ppm.

Keywords : Olopatadine Ophthalmic formulation, UV-spectrophotometer, method validation, reagents.

Introduction

Olopatadine (OLO) is chemically is dibenz[*b,e*]oxepin-2-acetic acid, 11-[3-(dimethylamino)propylidene]-6,11-dihydro-, hydrochloride, (*Z*)-; 11-[(*Z*)-3-dimethylamino-propylidene]-6,11-dihydrodibenz[*b,e*]oxepin-2-acetic acid, hydrochloride. The purpose of this study is to quantify the peroxide content in Ophthalmic formulation contain of 0.1% of Olopatadine drug used to treat itching and redness in the eyes due to allergies. The other ingredients along with drug in this formulation are polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), benzalkonium chloride, disodium orthophosphate, sodium chloride, ethylenediaminetetraacetate. Based on details of ingredients presents in Ophthalmic formulation. OLO active has been listed in USP monograph doesn't contain method of analysis for hydrogen peroxide estimation. Hence we attempt to develop the UV-spectroscopic method for estimation of peroxide content in Ophthalmic formulation, this is pre requested or mandatory to estimate peroxide content in formulation because it will af-

fect the drug stability in terms of the degradation. It is advised to maintain peroxide levels in any product less than 400 ppm suggested by European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur, 7th Ed.). This method is capable of detect peroxide content from 0.4 µg/g to 500 µg/g in specified formulation.

Instrumentation :

Agilent UV-Visible Spectrophotometer, model 8453 was employed with wavelength accuracy of ±0.5 nm, Mettler Toledo electronic balance was used for weighing the samples. Data collection and processing was performed using the Chemstation software. Wavelength was kept at 405 nm and 50 mm Quartz cuvette.

Materials :

Chemicals :

All chemicals used in this study were analytical grade. Hydrogen peroxide, titanium(III) chloride and sulphuric acid were purchased from Merck. 0.1% Olopatadine Oph-

thalmic formulation from marketed samples.

Reagents :

The 13% (v/v) sulphuric acid and titanium(III) chloride-sulfuric acid reagents were prepared as per the EP monograph specification (Ph. Eur, 7th Ed.).

Preparation of solutions :

Standard stock solution : Weigh accurately about 3.33 g of 30% w/v hydrogen peroxide (equivalent to 1000 mg of 100% (w/v) H₂O₂) in to 100 mL volumetric flask and dissolve in 20 mL of deionized water and make up to the volume with deionized water. Further, dilute 2 mL of this solution into 200 mL volumetric flask containing 20 mL of DI water and make up to volume with deionized water and mixed well.

Standard solution (10 ppm) : Transfer 5.0 mL of stock solution into 50 mL volumetric flask, add 5 mL of conc. sulfuric acid to the sample and mix the contents. (*Caution*; volumetric flask becomes hot). Place the volumetric flask in the water to attain the room temperature. Further, add and 2 mL of titanium(III) chloride sulfuric acid reagent and make up to volume with deionized water. Keep the solution aside for 30 min.

Sample blank solution : Pipette out accurately 25.0 mL of sample into 50 mL volumetric flask. Slowly add 5.0 mL of conc. sulfuric acid to the sample and mix the contents. (*Caution*; volumetric flask becomes hot). Place the volumetric flask in the water to attain the room temperature. Further, add about 19 mL of deionized water and 2 mL of 13% sulfuric acid. Keep the solution aside for 30 min.

Test solution : Pipette out accurately 25.0 mL of sample into 50 mL volumetric flask. Slowly add 5.0 mL of conc. sulfuric acid to the sample and mix the contents. (*Caution*; volumetric flask becomes hot). Place the volumetric flask in the water to attain the room temperature. Further, add about 19 mL deionized water and 2 mL titanium(III) chloride sulfuric acid reagent. Keep the solution aside for 30 min.

Results and discussion

Method development :

Proper wave length selection of the methods depends upon the nature of the sample and its solubility. To develop a rugged and suitable spectrophotometric method

for the quantitative determination of peroxide content, the analytical condition were selected after testing the different parameters such as acid concentration, solubility and analyte concentration. Our preliminary trials were by using different compositions of sulfuric acid and titanium(III) chloride reagents and concentration of formulation been used as a sample.

Scan standard solution in UV spectrophotometer between 400 nm to 800 nm on spectrum mode, using diluents as a blank. The λ_{max} value for peroxide was found at 405 nm. The proposed analytical method is comparatively simple, accurate and reproducible.

Method validation :

Analytical method validation (ICH, Q2B (R1)) is a process that demonstrates suitability of the proposed procedures is suitable for the intended purpose. More specifically, it is a matter of establishing documented evidence that provides a high degree of assurance that the method consistently provides accurate results to evaluate the product against defined specifications. The validation parameters such as specificity, accuracy, precision, linearity, limit of detection, limit of quantification and system suitability have to be evaluated as per the ICH guidelines using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

System suitability : Six scans were taken from single preparation solution and calculated %RSD for obtained absorbance at specified wavelength. The percentage RSD was found to be lesser than 2%.

Linearity : The linearity of the method is its ability to elicit test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of the analyte in the test solution. The calibration curve was taken in the range of 1.2–15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The correlation coefficient of the linearity was found to be 0.999 as shown in the Fig. 1 and results in the Table 1.

Fig. 1

Table 1

Sr. No.	Standard concentration in µg/ml details	Average absorbance at 405 nm
1.	1.2	0.1604
2.	5.0	0.5807
3.	8.0	0.9462
4.	10.0	1.1749
5.	12.0	1.4077
6.	15.0	1.7890
	R^2	0.999

Accuracy : Accuracy of the method is ascertained by standard addition method at 3 levels. Standard quantity equivalent to 80%, 100% and 120% with respect to Limit of Quantization (LOQ) levels were added in sample. The accuracy results shown that for spiked drug were obtained at each added concentration was found to be 96–99%, thus indicating that the developed method was accurate (Table 2).

Table 2

ppm peroxide in sample	ppm peroxide spike	Theoretical ppm peroxide	Measured ppm peroxide	% Recovery
0.79	1.2 (LOQ)	1.99	1.93	95.6
0.50	7.91 (80%)	8.41	8.15	96.9
0.50	9.89 (100%)	10.39	10.22	98.4
0.50	11.87 (120%)	12.37	12.20	98.6

Sample analysis :

Two different marketed formulations were analyzed for peroxide quantification using developed method and results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Sample details	Peroxide in ppm	Peroxide limit
Marketed formulation-1	0.50	10 ppm
Marketed formulation-2	0.79	

Conclusions

The proposed method for estimation of hydrogen peroxide in Olopatadine Ophthalmic formulation was found to be simple, accurate, economical and rapid. Hence, this method can be used for the quantification of peroxide content in Ophthalmic formulation.

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